

Selection of Sustainable Cutting Fluid Using Multi Criteria Decision Making

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ABSTRACT

The selection of sustainable cutting fluid is a major issue in metal cutting industries. To reduce frictional forces during metal cutting, the best cutting fluid is required which will have social, economic, and environmental impacts. In addition to having strong lubricating qualities, resilience to low temperatures, recyclability, and thermal, oxidative, and hydrolytic stability, the perfect lubricant should be the least costly, least poisonous, and least hazardous to the environment. In this Research, five different cutting fluids commonly used in machining processes have been discussed: Vegetable Oil (Canola), PAG, synthetic ester, mineral oil canola oil, TMPTO (tri methylol propane trioleate), synthetic ester, PAG (Poly-alkylene glycol), mineral oil. The optimal selection of these cutting fluids was determined using a combination of entropy-TOPSIS methodology a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods, based on criteria such as thermal stability, flash point, pour point, and viscosity index. The result shows that TMPTO gives better results than other cutting fluids.

KEYWORDS: Sustainable cutting fluid, Machining Operations, Entropy, TOPSIS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable cutting fluid plays a crucial role in metal cutting, which is the utmost requirement of any type of production. Various methods are used to reduce friction and enhance surface finish in machining, with cutting fluid being one of the most effective solutions. These fluids have several beneficial properties that must meet ASME standards (ASME, 1952). The properties should be:

- High heat absorption capacity is required to remove the heat from the tool and the work piece at a satisfactory rate.
- It should have good lubrication properties. The fluid film should be able to sustain high pressure present at the tool chip and tool-work piece interfaces.
- The coolant should have a high flash point, i.e., it should be non-flammable.
- The cutting fluid should not have solid precipitates at normal working temperatures.
- High-temperature stability is required to prevent the oxidation of the coolant and sticky deposits on the machined surface of work piece parts.
- The components of the cutting fluid should not easily become rancid, and no unpleasant odor should emanate when heated or used.
- It should not be either toxic or prone to contamination and have a long useful life. No harm should be caused to the machinist due to the sustained exposure of cutting fluid.
- It should be environment friendly to dispose and should be capable of being recycled.
- A cutting fluid should be inert so that it does not react with the tool, work piece, or machined parts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature survey reveals that a variety of cutting fluids are available in the machining industry. In this Research five kinds of cutting fluid have been used as follows:

a. Vegetable oil (Canola):

Due to the rising price of petroleum and its harmful impact on the environment, vegetable oil (Canola) was selected. It is a long chain fatty acid attached to hydroxyl groups through ester bonds with triglyceride molecules. Due to long chain fatty acid, it ensures an effective lubricating film which can reduce the wear and effect of friction (Fox et al., 2007; Ozcelik et al., 2013). (Fox et al., 2007; Debnath et al., 2014), Reported that these oils significantly improve the performance. (Kolawole et al., 2013) Peanut oil demonstrated superior fluidity, enhanced cooling capacity, and improved surface morphology compared to palm oil when used as a cutting fluid in machining. Vegetable oils, composed of triacyl glycerides, have desirable properties as lubricants, providing high strength films that reduce friction and wear on metallic surfaces.

b. TMPTO (Trimethylolpropane Trioleate):

Researchers are exploring the use of trimethylolpropane trifoliate (TMPTO) as an environmentally friendly lubricant additive. It is obtained from oleic acid produced from vegetable oil and polyol ester. TMPTO is highly biodegradable, so it is used as a green cutting fluid (Qiao et al., 2017). TMPTO is considered a bio-lubricant due to its low toxicity and biodegradability. Chemically sulfurized vegetable oil-based additives enhance TMPTO's lubricating capabilities, reducing friction and wear (Bachchhav et al., 2022). The study investigates the effects of TMPTO-based lubricant on thrust force and torque during high-speed drilling of Al-6061 and develops a machine learning model to predict high-speed drilling machinability.

c. Synthetic Ester:

Synthetic ester fluids, made from alcohol and fatty acids, are suitable for lubricant formulations, especially for applications over a wide temperature range. It consists of alcohol and fatty acids with carboxylate groups (Pettersso, 2007). These environmentally adapted fluids can be tailored to meet various needs, maintaining film thickness better under sliding conditions.

d. PAG (Poly-alkylene Glycol):

The fourth cutting fluid, also known as poly-alkylene glycol (PAG), contains a copolymer of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide (Tsai et al., 2014). It consists of copolymer of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide (Tsai et al., 2014).

e. Mineral Oil:

Mineral oil is an alternative cutting fluid made from petroleum-based base oils, produced through vacuum distillation (Mackerer et al., 2003). These oils contain undesirable aromatics, which can be carcinogenic and negatively impact product performance. Modern refineries reduce these aromatics through solvent extraction, catalytic hydro-treating, or hydro-cracking. Chronic exposure to poorly refined base oils can cause skin cancer. Refinery-specific operating conditions are needed to achieve adequate PAC reduction.

The Parameters of the alternatives selected in this study are Thermal stability (TS), Viscosity Index (VI), Flash point (FP) and Pour point (PP). The impact of the parameters is on machine surface as follows: -

i. Thermal Stability:

It is the temperature up to which the cutting fluids are stable and perform well. The property of the fluid degrades above this temperature. If the thermal stability increases the machining process goes well at elevated temperature. It is a beneficial factor for the machining process.

ii. Viscosity Index:

It is an index through which we can determine the change in viscosity of a cutting fluid with the change in temperature. It is a unitless parameter and it is beneficial for the machining process.

iii. Flash Point:

It is the minimum temperature at which a liquid creates vapor. Low Flash point can generate excessive heat during machining process which can reduce tool life due to increasing wear. Very high flash point is required to get benefit during machining process.

iv. Pour Point:

It is the temperature at which the flowability of the cutting fluid is ceased. So, a lower pour point is required to maintain the performance of the cutting fluid. It is Non beneficial factor for machining process.

The exact values of the above parameters could not be identified as some ranges of values are available in the online sources (Madanhire et al., 2016; Benedicto et al., 2017; Talib et al., 2019; Kavut et al., 2022; Leea et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022; Teh et al., 2022; Uppar et al., 2022; Malik et al., 2023; web-1; web-2; web-3; web-4; web-5). So average values of the mentioned parameters are taken for this study.it is presented in Table-1.

Table-1. Alternative cutting fluids and MCDM criteria and corresponding numerical data

(Madanhire et al., 2016; Benedicto et al., 2017; Talib et al., 2019; Kavut et al., 2022; Leea et al., 2022a; Lee et al., 2022b; Teh et al., 2022; Uppar et al., 2022; Malik et al., 2023; web-1; web-2; web-3; web-4; web-5).

Alternative/ Criteria	(TS)	(VI)	(FP)	(PP)
Vegetable Oil (Canola)	305	212	280	-24
Synthetic Ester	300	139	270	-45
TMPTO	230	187	310	-40
PAG	200	230	200	-15
Mineral Oil	322	100	135	-23

TS-Thermal Stability, VI-Viscosity Index, FP-Flash Point, PP-Pour Point

The following section discusses research conducted on this topic.

3. PROPOSED RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To study different parameters of selected alternatives Multi criteria decision model (MCDM) is used in this research. As the units of criteria are different it is not possible to compare the alternatives directly based on given criteria. So, weightage of each criterion is determined by using Entropy method which was proposed by Shannon (Shannon, 1948). Then the rank of the alternatives has been determined based on the mentioned criteria by following TOPSIS method which was developed by Hwang and Yoon (Hwang et al., 1981).

In this research, the following methodology has been developed:

Step – I:

The proposed work considered five numbers of cutting fluids based on various criteria such as Thermal stability (TS), Viscosity Index (VI), Flash point (FP) and Pour point (PP).

Step- II:

A decision matrix has been formed using alternatives and parameters which will be used to calculate weights of parameter. The equations involved in Entropy method (Singh et al., 2020) will be used to determine weights step by step.

Step- III:

A weighted decision matrix will be formed by using TOPSIS (Shanian et al., 2006; Sarkar, 2014) Methodology.

Step- IV:

The normalized decision matrix will be formed using TOPSIS Methodology.

Step- V:

The identification of positive and negative ideal solution sets involves determining the best (positive ideal) and worst (negative ideal) possible values (Dymova et al., 2013) for criteria in decision-making methods like TOPSIS. The positive ideal solution maximizes benefits, while the negative ideal solution minimizes undesirable outcomes.

Step-VI:

The rank of the alternative cutting fluid is calculated using TOPSIS Methodology.

4. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The result has been calculated as follows:

Step-I:

The decision matrix formed using alternatives and criteria as follows:

Table 1. Alternative cutting fluids and MCDM criteria and corresponding numerical data (Madanhire et al., 2016; Benedicto et al., 2017; Talib et al., 2019; Kavut et al., 2022; Leea et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022; Teh et al., 2022; Uppar et al., 2022; Malik et al., 2023; web-1; web-2; web-3; web-4; web-5).

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TS-Thermal Stability, VI-Viscosity Index, FP-Flash Point, PP-Pour Point

Step-II:

The weights of the parameters calculated as follows:

Pour Point: 0.440, Viscosity Index (0.240), Thermal Stability (0.095), Flash Point (0.225).

Step-III, IV, V:

The weighted normalized decision matrix with positive and negative ideal solution are calculated as follows:

Table-2. Positive and Negative ideal solution sets with weighted normalized matrix values identified by TOPSIS method

Alternative/ Criteria	(TS)	(VI)	(FP)	(PP)
Weighted Normalized Matrix (TOPSIS)				
Vegetable Oil (Canola)	0.047084236	0.126243519	0.114085552	-0.149968603
Synthetic Ester	0.046312363	0.082772873	0.110011068	-0.281191131
TMPTO	0.035506145	0.111356312	0.126309004	-0.249947672
PAG	0.030874909	0.136962308	0.08148968	-0.093730377
Mineral Oil	0.049708603	0.05954883	0.055005534	-0.143719911
Positive and Negative ideal solution sets (Sj+, Sj-)				
Sj+ Ideal Best	0.049708603	0.136962308	0.126309004	-0.281191131
Sj- Ideal Worst	0.030874909	0.05954883	0.055005534	-0.093730377

Step-VI:

The rank of the cutting fluids is calculated as follows:

Table-3. Distance values (Vi+, Vi-) to positive and negative solution sets, relative closeness coefficients (Pi) to the ideal solution and alternative cutting fluid selection ranking.

Alternative	Vi+	Vi-	Pi	Rank
Vegetable Oil (Canola)	0.132252	0.106603	0.446	3
Synthetic Ester	0.056689	0.197344	0.777	2

TMPTO	0.04282	0.179425	0.807	1
PAG	0.193662	0.081818	0.297	4
Mineral Oil	0.173134	0.05342	0.236	5

5. DISCUSSION

In this study, to select the optimal cutting fluid for machining process the weightage coefficients for the four criteria are identified following the Entropy method. Table-1 shows the decision matrix used in MCDM method. These weighting coefficients are calculated following the equations used in the Entropy methodology. The Pour Point criterion has the maximum weight that is 0.440, followed by the Viscosity Index criterion has the weight of 0.240. Whereas the Thermal Stability has the minimum weight that is 0.095. It is to be noted that all the criterion has positive relation with machining process except Pour Point. If Pour point is increased the flowability of the cutting fluid can be decreased at normal temperature and the Tool life reduced due to excessive wear. So lower pour point is always desirable.

After calculating the weights of the criteria following the Entropy method, selection of suitable cutting fluid is guided by TOPSIS method. The decision matrix from Table-1 is again used for this purpose. Then the weighted normalized matrix, positive and negative ideal solution sets (S_j^+ , S_j^-) are determined step by step following the equations used in TOPSIS method, mentioned in Table-2. The maximum and minimum values of each criterion can be found out from the same table. Table-3 represents the distance values to the positive and negative solution sets (V_i^+ , V_i^-), the relative closeness coefficients of the solution (P_i) and the rankings of alternative cutting fluids. It is identified from the rankings that the TMPTO has the maximum closeness coefficient. Hence TMPTO is the most suitable cutting fluid and ranked first. The next suitable cutting fluid is Synthetic Ester and ranked second followed by Vegetable oil (Canola) and PAG. Mineral oil has the least closeness co-efficient and it is ranked last. These ranking of the chosen cutting fluid may change if the criteria are altered.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Earlier a similar analysis of the same type of study was experimented considering the value of criteria in likert scale. The Researcher did not take the actual numerical value of the criteria. In this study actual numerical values are considered. The exact values of the above parameters could not be identified as some ranges of values are available in the online sources. So, average values of the mentioned parameters are taken for this study. The ranking of the chosen cutting fluid may change if the selected criteria are altered. The result shows that TMPTO is the best cutting fluid. Other methods like VIKOR and MOORA also can be utilized to find out the ranking of the cutting fluid based on the given parameters.

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